

European Parliament Proposes Reforms to Legislation Around Pharmaceutical Data Exclusivity

Issue/problem

The European pharmaceutical industry is facing a range of challenges, including unequal access to medicines across member states, high prices for innovative treatments, shortages of essential medicines, and the steady decline of the [EU's share of R&D funding](#) for new medicines between 2001 and 2020.

Description of the problem

The current European pharmaceutical legislative framework has not been updated in 20 years and faces specific problems associated with the development and marketing of new treatments. Currently, investment in developing medicines does not prioritize the greatest unmet medical needs, including rare diseases, and new medicines are introduced at different times across member states, with some EU countries never receiving new treatments.

Results

On [April 10](#), the European Parliament approved a package of reforms for European pharmaceutical legislation. This package aimed at replacing the current eight years of data protection and two additional years of market protection with a minimum regulatory data protection period of seven and a half years, during which other companies cannot access product data, and two years of market protection from generic and biosimilar products. In order to address unmet health needs, the package contemplates providing certain categories of drugs with longer periods of protection, such as those developed to treat rare diseases, which would have up to a total of 11 years of exclusivity.

Lessons learned

While approved by the prior European Parliament, the package will be revisited by the new cohort of members to be elected on June 6, 2024. Currently, the package sits with the European Council for review, with revisions expected in the fall of 2024. Negotiations between Parliament and the Council will continue until final agreement on the text is achieved, after which point the legislation can begin to be implemented. This means that reforms are likely to begin to alter the market in 2026 at the earliest.

There has been broad opposition to the proposed changes from industry. The [European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations](#) argued that the regulatory data protections should be held to a standard of eight years as initially introduced. [EuropaBio](#), the continent's largest biotech industry group, believes that the changes will harm the biotech ecosystem and lead to decreased investment, including in collaboration and partnerships to bring innovative treatments to market. Parliament will have the opportunity to adjust the proposal after the election before it becomes law and will engage in consultations with both member states and industry to inform its negotiations with the Council.